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'Irish twin transition efforts through Data Centres'

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Executive summary

Ireland is interested in the twin transition understood as the joint advancement of digitalisation and decarbonisation, focusing on data centres and other large energy users. The analysis is based on desk research and semi-structured interviews with academic experts and policymakers, and examines the design, governance, and implementation of relevant policy frameworks.

Ireland has developed an articulated policy architecture linking digital and climate objectives across multiple strategies. Digital technologies are framed as enabling tools for sustainability, particularly through improved data availability, system optimisation, and support for emissions reduction. At the same time, policy documents explicitly recognise the environmental impacts associated with digital infrastructure, notably in terms of energy demand, pressure on electricity grids, and resource use.

Within this framework, data centres are identified as a strategic sector. They contribute significantly to Ireland's digital economy and international competitiveness, while simultaneously representing a major and growing source of electricity demand. Policy responses therefore aim to reconcile these competing dynamics through a selective and planned approach to development. This includes prioritising projects that demonstrate efficient use of grid capacity, integration with renewable energy, and alignment with broader economic objectives.

The Government Statement on the Role of Data Centres establishes a set of guiding principles for sustainable development, including renewable energy additionality, co-location with future-proof energy supply, decarbonisation pathways, and contributions to local economic activity. The Large Energy-User Action Plan (LEAP) extends this approach to other energy-intensive sectors and introduces a more explicit spatial dimension, particularly through the identification of locations where industrial activity can be aligned with renewable energy infrastructure.

Evidence from interviews provides further insight into the functioning of this framework. While monitoring systems and analytical capacity are in place, interviewees emphasised that policy implementation remains largely non-binding, with limited enforcement mechanisms. In addition, stakeholder involvement appears uneven, with stronger engagement from institutional and sectoral actors than from local or smaller stakeholders. Interviewees also highlighted emerging distributional issues, including the spatial concentration of infrastructure and the uneven allocation of associated costs and benefits. Overall, the case study indicates that Ireland has established a coherent strategic framework for the twin transition. However, the effectiveness of this approach depends on the extent to which existing policy instruments can be translated into binding measures, coordinated across governance levels, and aligned with considerations of territorial and distributive balance.

1 Introduction

Globalisation has been accompanied by the parallel expansion of technological change and growing environmental awareness. In recent years, scholarly and policy attention has increasingly focused on the concept of the twin transition, which captures the extent to which digitalisation can support and accelerate sustainability outcomes [R29]. The concept of the twin transition has been adopted across a range of policy domains, including agriculture, construction, and mobility. Across these sectors, it is associated with a strong techno-scientific promise, framing digital technologies as key solutions to contemporary environmental challenges [R26].

A 2022 EU report framed the “twin transition” or rather the green and digital future where the use of specific technology produces less emissions and is useful to achieve green transition. The report provided guidelines for a (just) transition that is crucial for widespread acceptance of green-digital solutions [R43]. It is necessary to be able to link the parallel transitions running in parallel that are the digital and the green transitions. From this perspective, digital transformation constitutes a key driver of smart, inclusive, and sustainable growth, enabling both individuals and firms to contribute to the development of a more inclusive and sustainable digital society.

In the context of the ecological transition, the adoption and deployment of digital technologies enhance the availability of information, thereby supporting more sustainable decision-making by consumers and enabling firms to improve the environmental performance of their operations [R44]. Additionally, strategies of eco-innovation, where innovation strategies are directed to improve environmental sustainability, have a positive effect on reducing for instance energy consumption by technology itself [R44]. The latter is especially relevant to acknowledge the importance of technology to increase firms’ competitiveness and enabling them to expand their markets, product lines or offer additional services. Thus, while digitalisation may have an environmental cost it is currently considered a necessary element and item relevant in markets with a high demand. A high demand with a higher environmental cost that the same technology can mitigate.

Ireland has shown great interest and commitment in assessing and tackling the need to reduce emissions and fight climate change as well as remaining competitive and efficiently implementing digital measures. According to the European (EU) Database in 2025, about 26% of Irish firms (all sectors) were using ICT systems to reduce energy consumption, just above EU average (25%) [R30]. At the same time, Ireland is a major player in the global digital economy, with strength in high-tech activities and a pronounced concentration of information and communication technologies (ICT). In 2022, ICT generated 34.8% of the country’s gross value added—an EU-leading share. This profile is closely linked to the heavy presence of multinational firms, drawn by Ireland’s business-friendly tax setting and deep

pool of skilled labour [R22]. Regardless of this former and latter, Ireland still has the lowest EU public investment in R&D, with digitalisation being the largest % of their overall R&D. The latter EU report highlights that while digitalisation remains a country's priority alongside reducing emissions, the implementation is uneven.

In 2023, 66% of Irish small and medium enterprises (SMEs) demonstrated a basic level of digitalization [R25] acknowledging the need to connect rural areas and remain competitive. While Ireland performs as one of the European leader of the digital transition [R26] their green transition remains weak due to their firms' level of digitalisation. The latter demonstrated by EU's 2025 data recording that only 31% of firms had a high digital index¹ [EUROSTAT, R31] with the majority recording a low index. There are industrial stakeholders who are concerned with the energy efficiency and supply required for Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the ability for the Irish national digital infrastructure to support it [R25].

The objective of this case study is to examine how Ireland operationalises the twin transition by aligning digitalisation and decarbonisation within present coherent policy frameworks. More broadly, the case study seeks to evaluate whether this integrated approach effectively manages trade-offs between competitiveness, energy demand, and environmental sustainability. This case study was based on desk research and semi-structured interviews to academic experts and policymakers involved at a stage of the strategies and/or policies presented.

¹ The Digital Intensity Index (DII) is measured with a EU's structure indicator of knowledge and application of digital instruments [R32]

2 Twin transition in Ireland

The main reference to digitalisation and decarbonisation efforts, Ireland has the **Digital Ireland Framework**, a pathway to “assist people and businesses to realise the [...] efforts of digitalisation [...] more flexible and remote working and new job opportunities” [R17]. The framework expresses the willingness to achieve so via sustainable data centres that by collecting data provide support to mitigate and adapt to climate change. Additionally, a section of this framework reviews the energy that these centres require, providing a direction in 2021 to include, for instance, on-site generation or battery storage capable of covering their full electricity needs. To support the complete decarbonisation of the power sector, this on-site generation should also be able to operate using renewable fuels, such as green gas or hydrogen, as these become more accessible [R18].

This framework is complemented by **Harnessing Digital**. This policy provides an extensive national agenda for digitalisation divided into four dimensions: 1) Digital Transformation of Business; 2) Digital Infrastructure; 3) Skills; and 4) Digitalisation of Public Services.

Within these policy frameworks, **digital technologies are positioned as key enablers of decarbonisation, supporting climate mitigation and adaptation efforts, as well as biodiversity protection, through enhanced data collection and analytical capabilities**. At the same time, the policy explicitly recognises that these benefits are not automatic. The environmental footprint of digitalisation, particularly in terms of energy consumption, resource use, and waste generation, may be significant and, if unaddressed, could offset potential gains. As such, the policy emphasises the need for targeted interventions to ensure that digital technologies contribute positively to sustainability objectives. This includes a specific focus on improving energy efficiency and addressing circular economy challenges associated with digital systems. To this end, the government committed to conducting dedicated analyses of both the positive and negative environmental impacts of digital technological change, in consultation with relevant experts, to guide the development of more sustainable digitalisation pathways [R31].

BOX 1 Specific SME Support Scheme

Specific schemes are available for SMEs as presented in the country’s Enterprise Strategy [R35] when referring to data centres to leverage “...digital transformation for a smart greening” [R36]. Support schemes of these kinds include **Build Digital** or the **Digital Transition Fund** to support greener ICT adoption. Other more indirect efforts include the **Renewable Energy Support Scheme (RESS)** to pressure the use of renewable energy and ambition to increase community and citizen participation in renewable energy projects.

Different policy papers, data monitoring reports, and other governmental efforts to provide legislative priority and frameworks acknowledge digitalisation supporting sustainability. However, these efforts do not efficiently include diverse stakeholders, while appearing to give space to larger powers (ie. sectoral pressures) to make policy-related decisions, as evidenced by interviewees and previous studies which highlighted how in Ireland coordination across levels of government remained weak [R28]. The main barriers were feedback from local authority staff, the limited translation of national objectives into local policy documents, and the lack of clear guidance in national policies on how implementation should occur at local level.

Table 1 Summarised related policies by category and focus on Twin Transition

Category	Examples	Twin Transition focus level
Policies (Acts/Statements)	Climate Act 2015/2021; Project Ireland 2040; Data Centre Statement; Digital Ireland Framework; Harnessing Digital	Strongest links in planning and data centre policy
Policy Schemes	Build Digital; Digital Transition Fund	Provide support for a sustainable digitalisation
Projects / Plans	Climate Action Plans; National Broadband Plan; NDP infrastructure projects	Digital mostly seen as enabler; only CAP2025 recognises digital-climate tension
Public Activities	Climate Conversations; NDCA; Climate Action Week; Citizen Assemblies	Engagement important but not systematically twin transition focused

The interviews that were carried to both academics and politicians acknowledged the willingness of the State to collect data and assess the needs both internal and those affected by EU pressures. However, they also acknowledged the State's absence to bind certain policies and include more rural and smaller stakeholders in the process. What is observed is Ireland's efforts to collect feedback that is monitored, as observed by the various committees present, however, how this translates into policy changes or binding items that allow for these same to be inclusive both during policy writing as well as implementation appears absent.

One expert describes a holistic view of the situation in Ireland explaining Irish's challenge to include stakeholders in policy implementation and more generally in Ireland's climate (and digital) policies. They present the intersection issue in between knowledge production, public deliberation, and institutional capacity. It is a larger issue the way in which knowledge is generated and integrated into decision-making, placing the argument onto the government, rather than a policy-design issue. However, they acknowledge the capacity constraints of the government (i.e. funding, limited specialist coverage). The latter is tackled with the Climate Change Assessment(s) and the *Project Ireland 2040* (PR2040) analysis that bridges the

knowledge between factual analysis (academic, expert) to policymaking (government). However, it appears that the limit is the final element of translating all this information into implementation and efficient policies.

Another expert explained that Ireland has not operated in depth to present the policy trade-offs to the citizens who can choose which to select, promoting rather collective decision-making and highlighting the lack of mechanisms to operationalise it. It is about having a “...democractic model against a representative-only model”.

2.1 Energy-demanding Data Centres (and AI)

As digitalisation advances, data centres have become critical and rapidly expanding infrastructures at both the European and global levels, underpinning the growing demand for cloud computing, data storage, artificial intelligence, and digital services. However, this expansion is accompanied by significant challenges, particularly in terms of rising energy consumption. Data centres also generate notable environmental and climate pressures, driven by their intensive electricity requirements and substantial water use for cooling, as well as associated carbon emissions where energy sources remain carbon-intensive [R40].

According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), data centres are responsible for 1.5% of the world’s total yearly electricity consumption [R37]. The EU has been working towards energy-saving ambitions reducing final energy consumption by at least 11.7% by 2030. Additional to the high energy consumption, data centres require large quantity of water for cooling purposes and are manufactured requiring various raw materials that generate large quantities of electronic waste. Under the Action 5 of the EU’s Affordable Energy Action Plan, expected to start its implementation in 2026 [R38], the objective is to enhance coordination and strengthen the electric system.

Data centres are relevant towards national, European, and international innovation and technological advancement. The rise of Artificial Intelligence (AI) requires also greater power and demand. As underlined by the IEA, there is current uncertainty on AI demand and pace of its acceleration onto the market. The electricity consumption in accelerated servers (mainly driven by AI adoption) is expected to grow 30% annually (Figure 1) [R39].

Figure 1 Data centre electricity consumption by region (2020-2030); Source: [R39]

In 2025, the EU published the first report assessing the energy performance and sustainability of data centres in the EU [R41]. The data reported that Germany had the highest number of Data Centres (estimated 456, recorded 335), while Ireland among the lowest (estimated 123, recorded 18) (Fig.2)

Figure 2 Number of reporting data centres from the EU scheme (count); Source: [R41] own production

Ireland scored a Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE)² ratio below EU average (1.18 over 1.36 average PUE). Most data centres in Ireland have a size of 2-10 MegaWatts (MW). Positively, it measured a higher-than-average Waste Usage Effectiveness (WUE) meaning less water is used to deploy the same level of computing power. The latter data provided was collected by the EU and Ireland was mentioned as struggling to implement the necessary systems for effective data collection and monitoring. Thus, while there are the need and (standard) pressures to collect data, the challenges are several.

BOX 2. Next steps to promote the energy performance and sustainability of data centres in EU [R42]

In the 2025, a second document was produced by the EU to support Article 12(5) of Directive (EU) 2023/1791 on the energy performance and sustainability of data centres. It draws on reported data, supplemented where necessary, and assesses performance through a set of sustainability metrics and key performance indicators. Stakeholders expressed broad caution regarding the introduction of Minimum Performance Standards (MPS), emphasising that current data—based on only one reporting cycle—remain insufficient to establish reliable benchmarks. Key concerns relate to fairness and feasibility, as performance indicators such as PUE and WUE are highly dependent on local climate conditions, resource availability, and technological configurations, potentially disadvantaging certain regions and smaller or older facilities. Moreover, rigid standards may risk distorting markets and discouraging innovation. While some support exists for MPS in principle, stakeholders advocate for a gradual, flexible implementation—initially targeting new facilities, aligned with existing rating schemes, and supported by improved data quality, third-party verification, and climate-adjusted benchmarks. Overall, MPS are seen as viable in the long term, provided they are grounded in robust data and harmonised across the EU to ensure both effectiveness and fairness.

2.2 Data centres as core twin transition policies

In this policy context, Ireland proposes two main policy bodies and diverse commitments regarding data centres: the Government Statement on the Role of Data Centres in Ireland’s Enterprise Strategy, and further on, the Large Energy-User Action Plan.

The “Government Statement on the Role of Data Centres in Ireland’s Enterprise Strategy” is potentially the single strategy in Ireland that clearly frames the twin transition, placing data centres at the core of Irish economy [R8]. The main objectives regard: economic impact, grid

² PUE is defined as the ratio of total facility energy consumption to the energy consumed by the IT equipment representing the amount of energy (for cooling, power conversion, lighting, etc.) required to support the servers, storage and networking gear [R41].

capacity, renewable use, efficient location, decarbonised solutions, and SMEs and community benefits. This document [R8] recognises data centres as essential digital infrastructure underpinning Ireland’s broader technology ecosystem, productivity, and export-oriented growth, while also acknowledging that their rapid expansion creates substantial pressures on electricity demand, grid capacity, emissions reduction targets, and, to a lesser extent, water infrastructure.

The strategy sets out a selective and plan-led approach to future data centre development, based on six principles: economic impact, grid capacity and efficiency, renewable additionality, co-location with future-proof energy supply, decarbonisation by design, and SME/community benefits. The policy therefore does not appear to reject data centre growth per se but seeks to prioritise projects that generate stronger domestic economic spillovers, support renewable energy deployment, use grid infrastructure efficiently, and align with Ireland’s long-term decarbonisation objectives. A specific emphasis is placed on regional locations, corporate power purchase agreements, demand flexibility, renewable co-location, and the potential reuse of waste heat. Overall, the Statement presents data centres as both a strategic asset and a constraint, arguing that Ireland’s digital and green transitions can only remain complementary if future digital infrastructure is planned within the limits of energy system capacity and climate policy commitments. When focusing on the environmental efforts it refers to the country’s Climate Action Plan and other policies oriented to set environmental and climate objectives.

Building on this policy orientation, Ireland has further operationalised the governance of the twin transition through the introduction of the Large Energy-User Action Plan (LEAP) [R45]. This initiative extends the earlier focus on data centres to a broader category of energy-intensive sectors, embedding digitalisation and decarbonisation within a coordinated, plan-led framework. In particular, LEAP marks a shift from principle-based guidance to a more explicit spatial and infrastructural strategy, centred on the identification of “green energy parks” and the co-location of large energy users with renewable energy sources. By doing so, the policy aims to reconcile growing digital and industrial demand with binding climate targets and electricity system constraints, ensuring that future development contributes both to economic competitiveness and to the decarbonisation of the energy system. In this sense, LEAP can be interpreted as a consolidation of Ireland’s twin transition strategy, where digital infrastructure and energy policy are no longer treated as parallel domains but as interdependent components of a single, integrated policy framework. Major objectives are set to be delivered from 2026 onwards. A reference to EU’s deadlines, such as the National Energy Demand Strategy [R46] or other energy directives.

LEAP is expected to be advanced through coordinated action across government departments, with its implementation subject to regular monitoring and reporting to a Senior

Officials Group and the Cabinet Committee on Economy, Trade and Competitiveness. Nearly all actions are planned starting 2026.

Figure 3 “Green Park” Concept; Source: [R46, p.30]

Academic research on Ireland’s digitalisation in the green transition supports the idea that policy efforts are limited. Additionally, Ireland sets several policy objectives and opportunities for stakeholder engagement that does not yet entirely translate in binding laws that nudge behaviour.

In this context, the interview with the policymaker situated Irish digital and climate policy within the broader national development strategy. They confirmed that Ireland’s economic model remains heavily reliant on multinational technology firms and digital services, positioning data centres and digital infrastructure as central pillars of enterprise policy. The expansion of data centres is framed primarily in terms of economic growth, competitiveness and employment. However, the significant electricity demand creates pressure on national grid capacity and renewable deployment. This places digital strategy in direct interaction with climate and energy policy. In this context, the twin transition is not simply a matter of coordination between green and digital agendas, but a site of potential paradox. Digital expansion may increase energy demand at a time when decarbonisation requires rapid emissions reduction and system stability. Thus, underlying the relevance and need for cleaner energy, when reducing energy use in general is not an option.

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In terms of governmental policy implementation, the policymaker described a governance structure in which responsibility is distributed across multiple departments, including enterprise, environment, and energy authorities. However, coordination challenges emerge due to differentiated mandates. Therefore, the absence of a fully integrated decision-making framework creates friction in balancing the diverse objectives, such as emissions reduction, energy security, and grid resilience.

This institutional configuration affects inclusiveness in two principal ways: 1) Sectoral stakeholders with economic influence may have stronger access to decision-making processes, and 2) Communities affected by infrastructure constraints may experience limited formal channels to shape strategic decisions.

While consultation processes exist, strategic decisions regarding data centre approvals and grid allocation are often technical and centralised.

The policymaker recognises spatial inequality where infrastructures (i.e. data centres) are localised and benefits are unevenly distributed. However, there is an increase in energy demand even by citizens and the uneven distribution is also from the access to digital benefits. To support the latter limitation, Ireland has invested funding (210 million Euros) to provide adequate connection and digital literacy in schools [R47]. The former interviewee suggests that the latter factors within a digital policy, while formally part of the twin transition, can generate secondary inequalities unless managed within a distributive framework. Distributive framework is intended as a policy where a policy approach that decides how costs and benefits are shared across different groups. To resolve this issue, they suggest that recent policy responses have begun to introduce system-level constraints, including grid capacity considerations and regulatory oversight of data centre development. Overall, they mention that policymakers must navigate reputational considerations, investment climate stability, and regulatory predictability. There are internal governmental structural, human delays, and other interests (i.e. programmes already started) that may delay the effectiveness of creating and implementing twin-oriented policies. These efforts appear directed at addressing the digital divide while simultaneously minimizing environmental impacts.

2.3 Stakeholder mapping

As illustrated in Table 3, a wide range of stakeholders are involved in the formulation of the various strategies and policies considered. However, as depicted by qualitative insights gathered, the Irish policy framework is often perceived as less effective in translating these strategies into binding and enforceable measures. In terms of inclusion, Irish transition governance is described as formally cross-governmental but operationally centralised and siloed. For instance, while Climate Action Plans involve multiple departments, decision-making authority remains concentrated within key ministries. Departmental mandates and

budgetary structures reinforce institutional compartmentalisation, limiting the potential for integrated policy solutions.

Table 2 Stakeholders mapping

Name	Type	Role	Involved in Climate Policy
Department of Climate, Energy and the Environment	Government	Lead department for climate policy, climate legislation, carbon budgets, electricity and energy systems, and national communication infrastructure.	Oversees all Climate Action Plans (CAP 2019, 2021, 2023, 2025), coordinates carbon budgets, climate modelling, energy transition planning, public participation (NDCA, Climate Conversations) and reporting under the Climate Act. Involved in the Climate Action and Low Carbon Development (Amendment) Act 2021. [refers to the need of digitalisation]
Department of Enterprise, Tourism and Employment	Government	Responsible for enterprise policy, digital transformation, technology sectors, industrial strategy, and labour-market aspects of digitalisation.	Involved for the Data Centres Statement. [only one mentioning twin transition clearly]
Committee on Environment and Climate Action	Government	Scrutiny, hearings, recommendations, oversight of Climate Act & Climate Action Plans	Reviewed climate legislation held evidence sessions; raised issues of just transition, energy poverty; monitored CAP implementation.
Just Transition Committee (Commissioner)	Government	Coordinates transition support for regions affected by decarbonisation	Engaged with workers, local authorities, unions and communities; identified inequality impacts; fed lessons into national CAP just-transition measures, including the energy-related ones that affected the obligations for data centres.
Commission for Regulation of Utilities (CRU)	Market regulator	Oversees electricity & gas market regulation	Provided technical advice on energy security, demand management and digital-sector pressures; input to CAP and Data Centre Statement.

3 Data centres within the broader policy framework

A major element resulting from the interviews is a primary core tension between the technological adjustments (from the government perspective) and the structural socio-economic transformation (from the academic perspective). According to the interviewees, three main elements requires more effort on Ireland's policy implementation and reduce policy inclusion: 1) weak integration of public deliberation into final decisions; 2) fragmented knowledge production; 3) insufficient resourcing of holistic assessment.

Ireland's limitation on climate governance is presented as a structural political economy problem: the interviewees list the issues as sectoral power imbalances (limited to bigger and more powerful firms), institutional path dependency, or State-industry alignment.

In this context, they express a need to better coordinate digital expansion and energy demand within a coherent framework that embeds decarbonisation constraints into long-term development strategies. Ireland has aimed to assess the country's achievements towards fighting climate change [R1] [R2] and planned ahead for 2024 with a National Planned Framework with PR2040 [R4]. In PR2040, it was acknowledged that attempts to implement previous national strategies (i.e. the National Spatial Strategy in 2002 [R5]) was due to the 2008 economic crisis and derailing towards other objectives.

For PR2040, there were several stakeholder meetings carried out in 2016 with preliminary consultation events (June, 2016) and public engagement (September, 2016). These stakeholders included also dedicated committees (i.e. Infrastructure, Environment, and Climate Action Sub Committee). The resulting work is presented in the Climate Action Plan (CAP2025) that updates the Government's efforts to define actions needed to tackle climate change. As previously mentioned, there are diverse efforts placed into action by the Irish Government to define climate objectives that include diverse tasks more largely related to the general green transition (i.e. reskilling efforts or renewable energy schemes).

Several activities are organised to tackle environmental objectives:

- Just Transition Plan (Just Transition Committee - JTC);
- National Mitigation Plan (NMP);
- Long-Term Strategy to 2050;
- Transition to Low-Carbon Climate-Resilient Society;
- Climate Action Fund (CAF);
- National Dialogue on Climate Action (NDCA);
- Local Government, Regional Offices and EU Cities Mission.

For instance, the National Just Transition Fund set forward up to 22 million euros for projects focusing on training workers and generating sustainable employment in green enterprises [R6]. Considering the scarcity of twin transition direct policies, except for those previously

mentioned, Table 1 presents environmental related policies and the partial, absent, or clear frame of the twin transition included.

Table 3 Summary multilevel irish policies implementing twin transition

Name	Description
Climate Action and Low Carbon Development Act (2015) [amended in 2021]	An Act to provide for the approval of plans by the Government in relation to climate change for the purpose of pursuing the transition to a low carbon, climate resilient and environmentally sustainable economy. This Act also establishes the Climate Change Advisory Council [does not refer to digital] [R7]
Government Statement on the Role of Data Centres in Ireland's Enterprise Strategy (2022)	Sets out the government's policy approach to data-centre development, including guiding principles that prioritise projects delivering clear economic value while aligning with electricity-system constraints, grid efficiency, renewable energy and decarbonisation objectives. [R8]
Ireland's Long-term Strategy on Greenhouse Gas Emissions Reduction	Provides indicative pathways beyond 2030 to reach climate neutrality by 2050, linking shorter-term carbon budgets and annual climate action planning to a whole-of-society transition across sectors. [R11]
National Development Plan [connected to Project Ireland 2040]	Defines long-term public investment priorities that underpin the National Planning Framework and support population growth and balanced territorial development to 2040. [R2]

3.1 From policy governance to skills and education

Irish climate policy is described as a framework strongly influenced by European Union obligations. Interviewees supported the idea that climate ambition had been significantly **shaped by compliance pressures** rather than by endogenous political transformation. This suggests a reactive governance model in which policy development is often driven by externally mandated targets rather than domestic social consensus.

Furthermore, as an export-oriented, foreign direct investment-driven economy, Ireland faces structural constraints when attempting to reconcile enterprise policy with decarbonisation. High-emissions sectors such as agriculture and energy-intensive activities are politically and economically embedded, limiting the scope for radical transition measures. In this context, following one's interviewees reasoning, climate policy is negotiated within the boundaries of maintaining economic competitiveness.

The 2025 review from the Climate Council warned that Ireland was substantially behind the European Union (EU)'s and national emissions reduction targets by 2030 [R9]. The Council also warned that this delay can cause issues also to tackle shortages of skilled workforce, insufficient training opportunities, and protecting the most vulnerable members of society.

A policy example in this field is the **retraining and reskilling**, deemed essential as the economy and employment scenarios are diversifying also due to the digitalisation [R9]. SOLAS is the state agency responsible for future education and training (FET) and has published the Green Skills 2030 strategy [R19] in 2024. Regarding digitalisation, this report presents the skills gap for multiple industries, such as agriculture and energy and additionally improves social equity.

A monitoring study by the European Union [R22] indicates that Ireland has been relatively proactive in implementing the European Declaration on Digital Rights and Principles, recording 89 initiatives in total, including four launched in 2024. Activity is strongest in digital education, training and skills, while fewer measures have been identified in areas such as a fair digital environment and sustainability. In terms of on-the-ground effects, initiatives focused on putting people at the centre of the digital transformation appear to deliver the greatest impact, whereas measures aimed at safeguarding freedom of choice seem less tangible.

For instance, **the project Build Digital** [R23] aims “...to unite all construction and built environment stakeholders to drive integrated, interoperable digital data adoption across the industry to innovatively improve efficiency, productivity, and international competitiveness on a sustainable basis in Ireland.” The latest survey of this project (2024) [R24] showed that in this sector specifically, 70% had not started their “digital journey”.

The education, awareness raising and skills gap is also highlighted in the literature. Research studying over 1000 Irish citizens highlighted how there is an individual gap on climate change perception between the same where while individual Irish citizens more generally thought they would be willing to contribute to fight climate change, they also deemed it necessary for others to do the same [R10].

The **National Youth Assembly on Climate** [R12] serves as a key forum where young delegates can raise climate priorities and submit recommendations directly to the Government. The 2024 Climate Conversations exercise, summarised in a June 2025 report (based on almost 2,000 online responses) shows rising concern about climate risks, especially for future generations. It also reveals ongoing confusion about the emissions impact of everyday choices—people tend to undervalue the benefits of electric vehicles and overstate the role of recycling. One prominent suggestion is the creation of community climate hubs, which the Council supports as a practical way to strengthen local engagement and encourage wider participation in climate action. The main results showed that even youth thought that the issues were funding and accessibility [R12].

To further enhance proactivity, the Government launched the Climate Actions Work [R13] to engage the NDAC, providing funding for local activities, an interactive map to locate these same activities, and a communications campaign to share about these same. The National Climate Forum (NCSF) acts as consultative forums on climate matters meeting twice a year

and it is established by the Department of Climate, Energy, and the Environment. The objectives include disseminating the Climate Change in the Irish Mind (CCIM) [R14] focusing on the Irish's people's perception of financial situations, attitudes, and trust to climate change and (media) sources related to this topic.

The latest CCIM report (2024) [R15] observed that while the largest majority had only a moderate amount of climate change knowledge, an even higher percentage believed that it was led by human actions. The majority also believed that should be a high priority for the Government (about 44% higher than other answers) [R16] and there was a national majority opposition present as well. The latter meaning that when looking at policies (ie. banning coal, higher taxes on cars using petrol, or reducing national cattle herd to reduce GHG), there was still a quite present percentage opposing these. Overall, this opposition accounted for 62% of the sample studied for at least one policy but was not reflective of the underlying concerns against climate change that remained.

Overall, these patterns justify attention to public attitudes within the case study, as they show that the ***success of transition policies depends not only on scientific or technical rationale, but also on their political and social acceptability***. Climate policy appears increasingly embedded within a broader green transition framework, where emissions reduction is pursued together with objectives related to energy system resilience, sustainable infrastructure, and the environmental management of digital expansion.

Although policy rhetoric emphasises whole-of-government approaches, implementation remains shaped by administrative boundaries. Coordination challenges and limited cross-sector capacity can reduce the effectiveness of inclusive design intentions. Inclusiveness may be stronger in terms of formal engagement than in terms of redistributive justice. The design of climate measures continues to operate within pre-existing economic and institutional structures.

Some major issues include: 1) urban–rural divides, particularly in relation to transport dependence and infrastructure availability, 2) sectoral power asymmetries, notably the influence of agriculture and enterprise actors in shaping burden allocation, and 3) housing and energy vulnerabilities, where retrofitting and heating transitions create uneven cost exposure across income groups and tenure types. Overall, one expert's impression suggests that certain measures, as expressed in the policies regarding data centres, have been introduced without fully anticipating their distributive implications.

4 Drivers of twin transition

The section provides the main drivers of the twin transition in Ireland. As presented in the previous sections, the twin transition in Ireland is not entirely happening and it is mainly reserved to policies directed at reducing the environmental impact of data centres. The efforts are additionally parallel to climate policies aiming to go towards a green transition, while finding space for technology to place its course with low harm to the environment.

Table 4 Twin Transition Drivers in Ireland

Subcategory	Definition	Example
Societal Challenges		
Climate and Environmental Stress	Pressures from climate change, pollution, resource depletion [EU Pressures as well]	Binding carbon budgets under the Climate Action and Low Carbon Development (Amendment) Act 2021 require rapid emission reductions across transport, agriculture, and buildings.
Education and Skills	Social demand for skills needed in transition	Strong emphasis on reskilling and digital upskilling in enterprise policy, but uneven regional access to training opportunities.
Economic Dynamics		
Labour Market Pressures	Employment, wage levels, job creation	Just Transition measures linked to closure of peat and coal sectors aim to avoid regional job losses (e.g. Midlands).
Political Constrains		
Public Opinion	Social acceptance and resistance	Public consultation and Citizens' Assembly used to build legitimacy for climate action, but resistance persists on transport and agricultural measures.
Technological Developments		
Low-Carbon Technologies	Availability & affordability of alternatives	Retrofitting schemes and electrification strategies depend on households' upfront capacity to invest.
Digital Systems	Tools for administration or monitoring	Expansion of data centres central to economic strategy; digital monitoring tools used for emissions tracking and reporting.
Legal Landscape		

New Regulations	Legislative changes impacting policy	Climate Action and Low Carbon Development (Amendment) Act 2021 establishes legally binding carbon budgets.
Institutional Capacities		
Administrative Ability	Ability to design & deliver policy	Strong central planning capacity for climate governance, but uneven delivery capacity at local authority level.
Access and Use of Evidence		
Evidence-Based Policymaking	Use of data and research in decision-making	Carbon budgets informed by Climate Change Advisory Council modelling.
International Relations		
EU Policy Pressures	Climate Policies	Ireland was involved in the drafting of EU policies for both climate change as well as digitalisation. While interest is present, it is unclear the integration at National level.

As the drivers highlight, it appears that although the policy implementation is weak, various are the pressures for a policy directed towards the twin transition. The next graph highlights the assumptions and policy rationale behind the policy landscape. The main item of interest for data centres is that it refers mainly to enterprises, since citizens are non-direct users of such service. Any decision to make a difference is focused on the industrial and political level.

Figure 4 Summary table on Ireland's twin transition

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5 Conclusion

Ireland presents a clear and structured approach to the twin transition, treating digitalisation and decarbonisation as closely interconnected policy priorities. Data centres sit at the centre of this strategy, reflecting both their economic importance and their implications for energy demand and emissions.

The analysis shows that Ireland has developed a relatively coherent policy framework linking digital and climate objectives, notably through its national digital strategy, the Government Statement on data centres, and the Large Energy-User Action Plan (LEAP). These policies recognise both the enabling role of digital technologies in supporting sustainability and the environmental pressures they create, especially in relation to electricity demand, grid capacity, and infrastructure planning.

Data centres are treated as a central component of Ireland's growth model, underpinning digital services, innovation, and international competitiveness. At the same time, their expansion raises clear tensions with decarbonisation targets and the capacity of the electricity system. In response, the policy framework adopts a selective and plan-led approach, favouring developments that can demonstrate efficient grid use, renewable energy integration, and wider economic benefits. LEAP extends this logic to other very large energy users and introduces a stronger spatial dimension through the idea of co-locating energy-intensive activities with renewable supply.

The interviews add an important layer to this picture. They confirm that the Irish state is active in collecting evidence, monitoring pressures, and responding to EU requirements, but they also point to weaknesses in implementation. In particular, interviewees stressed that many policy ambitions remain strategic rather than binding, and that smaller, rural, and locally affected actors are not always meaningfully included in policy design. They also highlighted concerns around spatial inequality, noting that infrastructure and benefits are unevenly distributed, while the burdens associated with energy demand and access to digital gains are not shared equally.

The evidence suggests that, while institutional structures for monitoring and coordination exist, they do not consistently translate into binding or inclusive policy outcomes. This limits the capacity to address distributional effects, particularly those linked to the spatial concentration of infrastructure and unequal access to its benefits.

Overall, the Irish case illustrates that managing the twin transition requires more than strategic alignment. It appears to be depending on the ability to translate policy intentions into coordinated, enforceable, and inclusive actions.

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